

Employee Performance Improvement Through Organizational Culture and Work Discipline at the Information Communications Service (Diskominfo) Purwakarta Regency

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Abstract

Many elements affect employee performance both from inside and from the organizational environment where the employee works. Of the various elements which can be taken into consideration crucial in employee performance, it may be categorised into two factors, namely organizational subculture and paintings area. The cause of this take a look at became to decide how tons affect Organizational way of life and work field have on worker overall performance on the statistics Communications provider (DISKOMINFO) Purwakarta Regency. This observe uses descriptive and verification methods in which the populace is taken from the workplace of conversation and records information (DISKOMINFO) Purwakarta Regency, using saturated sampling approach in sampling, that is carried out due to the fact the population is surprisingly small. facts processing is performed by more than one Linear Regression analysis, coefficient of willpower, and hypothesis trying out. Based totally on the outcomes of the calculation of the coefficient of willpower and speculation checking out, it suggests that organizational culture has a substantial impact on the worker overall performance variable, paintings field has a big effect on the employee overall performance variable.

Keywords: *Organizational Culture, Work Discipline, Employee Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

Management of Human resources (HR) is crucial in accomplishing dreams. usually, organizational leaders assume true overall performance from every worker in wearing out the tasks assigned by way of the enterprise. The employer realizes that human assets are the primary capital in the procedure of organizational development or even nationally, consequently the first-class of human assets ought to continually be evolved and directed with a purpose to achieve the desires set through the organisation.

The workplace of communication and information of the Province of Purwakarta Regency is an elaboration of government law no. 41 of 2007 regarding the agency of local apparatus. The Purwakarta Regency conversation and data workplace was formed primarily based on local law wide variety 9 of 2016 regarding the formation and composition of Purwakarta Regency regional equipment on November 4, 2016, and Regent regulation (PERBUP) wide variety 148 of 2016 regarding the location and organizational structure of responsibilities and capabilities in addition to working procedures of nearby apparatus 23 November 2016. This new service is a combination of several elements from separate fields that exist within the local government of Purwakarta Regency, namely the kaharti section of the Purwakarta Regency Secretariat. Based on the results of observations that have been made from reality and the many criticisms and complaints of DISKOMINFO employees, it turns out that the quality of service from the service is in the sufficient category. This is based on the number of criticisms and complaints of employees such as cooperation between employees that has not been maximized. The employee's performance has not been maximized, of course, cannot be separated from organizational culture factors and the discipline applied. In terms of employee attendance discipline, there has been a decrease in the level of employee absenteeism and the number of employees who are not present without explanation, especially at the Purwakarta Regency Communication and Information Office 2018 to 2019 decreased.

Culture is a very important factor in increasing organizational effectiveness. Organizational way of life may be the principle device of aggressive advantage, when the organizational culture supports the organization's strategy and can answer or overcome environmental challenges quickly and appropriately. Culture has the strength to steer an organization, it'll have an impact on the whole lot from who's promoted and what selections are made. Sometimes the subculture is fragmented and tough to study from the outside. The paintings subculture is likewise very robust and potential, all and sundry is aware of the company's desires and works to acquire them. Seeing this impact, subculture

has a massive have an impact on on worker performance. The organizational subculture withinside the Purwakarta Regency Communication and Information Office has now no longer been maximized, which may be visible from the effects of the pre-survey below:

Table 1. Results of the Pre-Survey form on structure Culture at the Communication and Information Office of Purwakarta Regency in 2020

No	Dimension	Frequency (F) Employee Answers					Total Score	Average Score
		SS	S	KS	TS	STS		
1	Innovation	4	6	9	1	0	73	3,75
2	Attention to detail	3	6	11	2	3	76	3,8
3	Result Orientation	3	7	6	4	1	70	3,5
4	People Orientation	4	8	3	3	2	69	3,45
5	Team Orientation	1	7	9	2	1	1	3,25
6	Aggression	2	3	10	3	2	60	7
7	Work Stability	1	4	13	2	0	67	3,35
Average								3,44

Source: Pre-Survey Results 2020

Based on this, the formulation of the matter during this study is:

1. How is that the influence of structure culture on worker performance at the Department of Communication and information of Purwakarta Regency?
2. How will the work discipline of workers have an effect on the performance of employees at the Department of Communication and information in Purwakarta Regency?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational culture

A strong organizational culture supports the company's goals, whereas a weak or negative culture hinders or contradicts the company's goals. According to Robbins & Judge (2012) structure Culture could be a system of shared that means control by members that distinguishes one organization from another. Then Mangkunegara (2013) structure culture is a set of assumptions or belief systems, values, and norms developed at intervals the organization that are used as activity tips for its members to beat external and internal adaptation problems. in keeping with Osborn and Plastrik, (2002) argue that, Work culture is a set of behavioral feelings and psychological frameworks that are deeply internalized and shared by members of the organization. According to Kinicki and Fugate (2013), organizational culture is used to provide implicit assumptions in a group as a guide and determination of perspectives, ways of thinking, and reacting to various environments.

According to Robbins (2008), there are seven main characteristics as an entire that are the essence of culture or culture, specifically (1) Innovation and the braveness to take dangers (the quantity to which personnel are encouraged to be innovative and dare to take risks). (2) attention to element (the degree to which personnel are predicted to exercising precision, analysis and interest to element). (3) effects orientation (the diploma to which control focuses greater on consequences than at the techniques and methods used to reap the ones effects. (four) human beings orientation (the diploma to which control choices bear in mind the results of those outcomes on humans in the company). (5) group orientation (the degree to which paintings activities are organized in groups in preference to individuals. (6) Aggressiveness (the degree to which humans are aggressive and aggressive rather than informal. (7) stability (the degree to which organizational activities emphasize keeping nation in evaluation to growth)

Work Discipline

In this case Hasibuan (2013) who argues that discipline is a form of awareness and availability of individuals to obey a rule and norms that apply within the company. therefore, it can be stated to be disciplined if personnel are inclined to perform all their duties and responsibilities with full consciousness. due to the fact area is the important thing to the employer's achievement, it must be enforced in a organization corporation to reap shared goals and expectancies. within the opinion of Harlie (2010), the signs of work subject are as follows: (1) constantly arrive on time (2) always prioritize the percentage of attendance (three) always follow and obey the provisions of working hours (4) constantly use operating hours with green and powerful as viable (5) have the talents and work skills in their discipline of duty (6) have a completely excessive morale (7) have correct conduct (8) always have creativity and innovation in doing work. paintings discipline is an operative function of human useful resource control which is very critical, because the higher the work field of an worker, the better the overall performance and work that can be accomplished, but if there's no utility of accurate work field it'll be tough for a organisation to get outcomes. most effective (Hasibuan, 2013). Work

discipline itself is not only useful for achieving company goals, but also for employees because work discipline can increase work enthusiasm and employee morale. According to Sinambela (2016) discipline is also useful for educating employees in obeying and complying with existing regulations, procedures, and policies so as to produce good performance. To maintain and improve good discipline is quite difficult because there are many factors that influence it.

Employee Performance

Performance can basically be interpreted as a person's success in doing a job, good performance is performance that follows procedures or procedures according to established standards. According to Sedarmayanti (2010), performance is the result of a person's work, where all of these results can be proven significantly and can be measured. Performance can be assessed and measured objectively can increase employee motivation to work better, but if performance is assessed subjectively and there is no clear measurement will cause employees to be demotivated and dissatisfied at work (Sinambela, 2016). According to Mangkunegara (2013), factors that can affect employee performance in carrying out their duties can come from two factors, namely individual factors and environmental factors in an organization. Companies can improve the performance of their employees if their employees have the awareness to be obedient and obey all the rules that exist in the company. Organizational environmental factors can also affect an employee's performance, a good work environment will be able to make it easier for an employee to carry out his work because an employee will feel helped by his physical work environment and will feel more comfortable working with his non-physical environment, by paying attention to work discipline and a person's work environment. Employees will have excellent performance so that company goals can be achieved. According to Mangkunegara (2013), worker performance is a result of labor in first-rate and amount that can be completed with the aid of an employee in carrying out his obligations in accordance with the responsibilities which have been given to him. worker performance is a state or spirit possessed by personnel in every task they do. According to Rivai (2004), worker performance is a real conduct that isn't proven by means of anyone as paintings performance produced by way of personnel in accordance with their function inside the employer. the dimensions of character employee performance are: 1) excellent of work 2) quantity of work 3) Punctuality 4) capacity to paintings (Damayanti et al., 2018).

Framework Research

Mas'ud in Kartiningsih (2015) states that organizational tradition is a machine of meanings, values and beliefs that are shared in an business enterprise that turns into a reference for action and distinguishes one agency from every other. Organizational subculture is the identification or essential man or woman of the organisation this is maintained and maintained. Mas'ud additionally stated that a sturdy way of life is a useful tool to direct conduct, because it enables employees to do a better task so that each employee at the start of his career needs to understand the tradition and the way the lifestyle is carried out. According to Robbins (2015) there are 7 main characters, all of which become important elements of organizational culture, namely: innovation and risk taking, attention to detail, orientation to results, orientation to towards individuals, team orientation, aggressiveness and stability. The author suspects that there is a positive influence of organizational culture (X1) on employee performance (Y).

H1: The have an effect on of Organizational tradition on worker performance.

Consistent with Rofi (2012), worker paintings field is the most dominant element so that paintings area wishes to be improved so that all worker expectations can be executed and get a job delight. This can improve the performance of the employee. Companies must provide sanctions for employees who violate the rules and carry out stricter supervision to improve employee performance (Dwipayana, 2014). The sanctions given must be appropriate so that employees who violate company rules and regulations do not make the same mistakes (Krisnanda & Sudibya, 2014). based on preceding studies on paintings area and employee overall performance, it could be concluded that the speculation is a temporary assumption of the issues that exist in the examine. in this look at the authors suspect that there may be a advantageous have an effect on of labor discipline on worker overall performance. in this examine, work field is an X (independent variable) that's an man or woman's capacity to comply with the regulations and norms that exist in the agency. meanwhile, employee overall performance as Y (certain variable) which is the duty and paintings outcomes of employees in accordance with the pleasant and quantity as well as agency policies. the writer suspects that there's a nice impact of labor subject (X2) on worker overall performance (Y).

H2: The influence of work subject on worker performance.

METHOD

The studies method used in engaging in this research is descriptive evaluation and verification method. Descriptive method is a studies technique carried out to explain and explain the state of affairs concerning statistics, characteristics of the populace based at the statistics that has been gathered, which is compiled systematically and then analyzed to get

conclusions, and solution the formula of the problem. whilst the verification method is a research approach that pursuits to decide the connection among two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2012).

Primarily based in this look at, due to the fact the population is not greater than a hundred respondents, the authors take one hundred% of the population at DISKOMINFO, specifically sixty three respondents. accordingly using the whole population while not having to draw a research sample as a unit of observation is referred to as a census approach. The collection of data that has been taken is based on sources, namely there are primary sources and secondary sources (Sugiyono, 2018). Primary sources are taken from the data taken which has been obtained through observations, questionnaires, and interviews. The secondary data sources were obtained but not taken directly through media related to the company or other parties (Indriantoro, 1999). Statistical processing approach using multiple linear regression approach using software program (SPSS). facts processing with SPSS utility produces outputs within the shape of normality, correlation, linearity, more than one linear regression values.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the data collected, it is known that respondents for gender characteristics, the majority of employees of the Department of Communication and Information (DISKOMINFO) Purwakarta Regency in this study were male as many as 46 respondents (73%). Furthermore, for the age that dominates at the age of 31-45 years as many as 53 respondents (84%) while the characteristics of the latest education, the majority of employees have a bachelor's degree as many as 26 respondents (41%) and for the majority of working years >15 years as many as 40 respondents (63%).

Validity Analysis

Validity take a look at is used to degree the validity or validity of a questionnaire. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the questions about the questionnaire are capable to show something that will be measured by means of the questionnaire (Ghozali, 2005). The results of the validity analysis distributed to 63 respondents for each item are as follows:

Table 2. Validity Test

Item	Correlation score	Probabilitas	Description
OC	0.651	0.2480	Valid
OC	0.676	0.2480	Valid
OC	0.753	0.2480	Valid
OC	0.755	0.2480	Valid
OC	0.759	0.2480	Valid
WD	0.704	0.2480	Valid
WD	0.751	0.2480	Valid
WD	0.732	0.2480	Valid
WD	0.849	0.2480	Valid
WD	0.850	0.2480	Valid
EP	0.745	0.2480	Valid
EP	0.760	0.2480	Valid
EP	0.813	0.2480	Valid
EP	0.726	0.2480	Valid
EP	0.832	0.2480	Valid

Source: Data Processing Results

Based on Table 2, the validity test for all the questions tested shows that from the three variables, all items have a probability score correlation of r results <0.05 , while the items that fall for each factor are non-existent, thus the instrument for Organizational Culture, Work Discipline, and Employee Performance meet the Validity test.

Reliability Analysis

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Alpha (a)	Status
Organizational Culture	0,654	Reliabel
Discipline Work	0,763	Reliabel
Employee Performance	0,691	Reliabel

Source: Data Processing Results

The results of the reliability test suggest that each one variables have a big enough alpha coefficient, which is above 0.60 so that it may be stated that everyone measuring standards of every variable from the questionnaire are reliability measuring tool.

Normality Test

Table 4. Data Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Organizational culture	Work Discipline	Employee Performance
N		63	63	63
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	3.9444	3.8889	3.8889
	Std. Deviation	.37808	.34978	.38055
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.458	.502	.482
	Positive	.397	.364	.363
	Negative	-.458	-.502	-.482
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		4.349	4.766	4.568
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.893	.617	.808

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results

Table 4 suggests that the significance stage of the research variables is commonly dispensed, this will be visible from the importance of the importance stage at the variables ranging above = 0.05. This indicates that the studies pattern is normally dispensed at an blunders charge of 5%.

Multicollinearity

Table 5. Multicollinearity

Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Organizational culture	.786	1.272
	Work Discipline	.786	1.272

a. Dependent Variabel: Employee Performance

From the calculation consequences within the desk above, the tolerance value is above 0.1 and the value Inflation issue (VIF) is below 10, so it may be concluded that there may be no multicollinearity between the independent variables.

Multiple Linear Regression Equation Analysis

Multiple regression analysis become used to measure the impact among organizational way of life and work field on employee performance. by using the usage of the SPSS 20 application, the values for more than one regression are received as follows:

Table 6. Regression Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients
		B	Std. Error	Beta
1	(Constant)	1,267	2,574	
	Organizational culture	,629	,111	,557
	Work Discipline	,315	,108	,287

a. Dependent Variabel: Employee Performance

Based on Table 6 above, multiple regression equations can be arranged as follows: $Y = 1.267 + 0.629 X_1 + 0.315 X_2 + e$

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Model Summary^U

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.729 ^a	.532	.516	1.31071

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Discipline, Organizational culture

b. Dependent Variabel: Employee Performance

From table 7 above, it is known that the coefficient of determination is 0.532 or 53.2%, meaning that the organizational culture variable (X1) and Work Discipline (X2) have an influence on Employee Performance (Variable Y) of 53.2% and the rest of 46.80% influenced by other factors. For example: career development, compensation and others.

Model Testing (F Test)

In step with Ghozali (2011), the goodness of suit test is carried out to degree the accuracy of the pattern regression function in estimating the real cost statistically. The goodness of in shape version may be measured from the statistical cost of F which indicates whether or not all the unbiased variables blanketed in the version have a joint have an impact on at the established variable.

Table 8. Model Testing (F Test)

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	117.145	2	58.572	34.094	,000 ^b
	Residual	103.078	60	1.718		
	Total	220.222	62			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Discipline, Organizational culture

b. Dependent Variabel: Employee Performance

Based totally on the ANOVA table above, a significance of 0.000 can be received where the wide variety is <0.05, so the hypothesis is time-honored, because of this it indicates that this version check is viable to be used in research.

T Test

The t-test become conducted to decide the impact of organizational culture and work field partially on performance, which become examined at a significant degree of 0.05 with the basis of selection making by searching on the comparison price between the tiers of sig <0.05 in order that the hypothesis can be commonplace.

**Table 9. t-Test Results
Coefficients^a**

Model	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	,492	,624
Organizational culture	5,680	,000
Work Discipline	2,927	,005

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based at the consequences above, organizational subculture has a sig stage of 0.00 so it can be concluded that the hypothesis is time-honored, which means that organizational subculture has a sizable effective effect on overall performance, as well as paintings area has a sig level. $0.005 < 0.05$ so it may be concluded that the hypothesis is everyday, meaning that work discipline has a great tremendous effect on overall performance. Personnel who display a high level of vigilance at work will have an excellent impact on using time at work.

The influence of organizational culture on employee performance

Employees who show a high level of vigilance at work will have a good impact on the use of time at work. Employees who are able to pay attention to every problem in detail will have good quality work. In addition to employees who are able to be oriented to all interests, employees can work together in working well. Employees who are able to show high morale will have an effect on good performance. The attitude of work enthusiasm might be transmitted to other personnel so that it may shape a very good organizational culture as well. The effects of this look at are in step with research through Harlie (2012), Venty Hertina Maulani (2013), Jessica Clairine (2014), Paksi Dwi Setyo (2015), organizational way of life has a advantageous and giant impact on worker performance. And that is in assessment to the studies of Jagarin Pane and Sih Darmi Astuti (2009) which states that organizational subculture has no impact on worker performance.

The effect of work subject on employee performance

Personnel who demonstrate moral work and are oriented to all employee pastimes could have a positive effect on cooperation in work. Adherence to work rules and paying attention to each trouble in detail will affect the great of correct work for employees. Employees who've good attendance and are aggressive at paintings have a great effect on the effectiveness and efficiency of personnel at work. So, paintings subject and organizational subculture together could have a superb and vast impact on worker performance. This suggests that the higher work subject and organizational culture will have an impact on the extent of employee performance. this is bolstered by means of the consequences of studies via Radeswandri and Utami (2013), Ilham Khaliq Marnis (2013) and Paksi Dwi Setyo (2015) that work subject has a wonderful and tremendous effect on worker performance.

CONCLUSIONS

Based totally at the effects of the have a look at, it may be concluded that organizational subculture and paintings subject partially have a fine affect on worker performance, and both simultaneously have an effect of fifty three 2%. This suggests empirically organizational subculture and paintings subject are elements that need to be evolved in accomplishing a employer aim.

The researcher suggests using other indicators outside of research that are able to explain the three variables more comprehensively. The researcher also suggests expanding the scope of the research and increasing the number of respondents so that the research results are more representative.

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